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Flexural Behavior of RC Beams made from Normal and High-strength Recycled Aggregate Concrete

C.S. Rangel¹, M. Amario², M. Pepe³, E. Martinelli⁴ and R.D. Toledo Filho⁵

ABSTRACT: The use of recycled aggregates for the production of new concrete is a viable solution for reducing the environmental impact of construction materials. Nevertheless, understanding the peculiar mechanical behavior and failure mechanisms of Recycled Aggregate Concrete (RAC) and their influence on the structural performance of Reinforced Concrete (RC) members is essential for promoting the use of these more sustainable materials in structural applications. This paper reports the results of experimental tests aimed at investigating the influence of using Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCAs) in concrete beams loaded in bending. Particularly, two RAC mixtures were designed, according to the well-known Compressible Packing Model (CPM), to achieve compressive strengths of 25 and 65 MPa. Reference mixtures, characterized by the same expected strength, were realized by employing ordinary crushed aggregates, whereas the corresponding RAC ones were obtained by replacing 50% (in volume) of the coarse fraction of ordinary aggregates with RCAs in the same size ranges. The mechanical behavior of these concrete mixtures was characterized by means of compressive and splitting tests, whereas the structural response was investigated by performing bending tests on RC beams. The results showed that, both for normal- and high-strength concrete under consideration, the use of RCAs affects neither the resulting mechanical properties of materials, nor the structural performance of the tested members.

1 INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is one of the economic sectors characterized by a high environmental impact, mainly due to emissions of pollutant gases, high energy consumption, huge raw material demand and production of waste, often undisposed (Moll et al, 2005). Since concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials, enhancing sustainability in its production processes would contribute to reducing the aforementioned environmental impacts of the construction sector (Meyer, 2009). To do so, the use of Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCAs) as a (partial-to-total) replacement of ordinary ones is a technically feasible and environmentally effective solution to produce a sustainable construction material. The latter is often referred to as Recycled Aggregate Concrete (RAC) (Koenders et al, 2014) and the most up-to-date codes and guidelines already provide indications about its production and application (M.II.TT., 2008; HKBD, 2009).

However, replacing NAs with RAs has an impact on the resulting properties of concrete. In fact, since RCAs have a more complex structure consisting of NAs and the so-called Attached Mortar (AM), they usually present lower density, higher porosity and, hence, higher water absorption capacity with respect to NAs (Fathifazl et al, 2006). Consequently, RAC presents higher water absorption, lower performance in durability

¹ *PhD candidate, COPPE/Federal University of Rio de Janeiro-Brazil, carolrangel@poli.ufrj.br*

² *PhD candidate, COPPE/Federal University of Rio de Janeiro-Brazil, mayara_amario@poli.ufrj.br*

³ *PhD, University of Salerno, mapepe@unisa.it*

⁴ *Associate Professor, University of Salerno, e.martinelli@unisa.it*

⁵ *Professor, COPPE/Federal University of Rio de Janeiro-Brazil, Toledo@coc.ufrj.br*

and, hence, weaker mechanical performance in comparison to a reference ordinary concrete, only made of NAs (Kenai and Debieb, 2015).

Therefore, many studies are being developed to understand and control the rheological, mechanical and durability properties of RAC: they consider also the influence of alternative processing techniques for RCAs (Pepe et al, 2014), variations in the curing conditions (López Gayarre et al, 2014), and generally demonstrate that specific mix-design rules are needed for RAC. However, these studies usually address the material behavior, but very limited research has been developed on the structural behavior of members made of RAC. In fact, since compressive strength does not control all the aspects of structural performance of RC members, observing the former is not generally sufficient to predict the latter. For instance, Sadati et al (2016) tested large scale RAC beams made by both replacing the coarse fraction of NAs with RCAs of similar sizes and employing Fly Ash (FA) as a partial replacement of Portland cement. The study demonstrated that, although compressive strengths of RAC were significantly higher than the corresponding reference concrete, the shear capacity of beams made of the former come out to be between 10 and 18% lower than the reference. This is probably due to the modifications in the complex mechanisms (i.e. shear friction, aggregate interlock, dowel effect, etc.) contributing to the shear strength in RC beams. Similar results were obtained by Arezoumandi et al. (2013) whose RC beams made of RAC with 100% of NAs replacement exhibited a reduction in shear capacity of about 12%. Besides this reduction, which was somehow expected, Arezoumandi et al. (2013) observed that the formulae provided by international standards generally overestimate shear strength and, hence, the existing formulations cannot be utilized for members made of RAC.

As for the flexural behavior, no significant variations were observed by Pacheco et al (2013), whose RC beams made of RAC, with a complete replacement of NAs, did not show any significant change in terms of force-deflection response, also because high-quality RCAs obtained by crushing discarded elements of precasting industry were actually employed. Moreover, Arezoumandi et al. (2013) observed that the flexural strength of RAC beams made with 100% RCAs is similar to the one of the corresponding reference beam. However, both higher deflections and closer cracks were observed, and the corresponding predictions based on the existing standards are generally inaccurate.

The short review of the literature highlights that further studies are requested for understanding the structural performance of RC members made of RC. Particularly, there is a specific lack of information on crack propagation and failure mechanisms. Therefore, this study aims at contributing to the advance of knowledge on these aspects, as it presents the results of experimental tests intended at investigating the flexural behavior of RC beams made of RAC. More specifically, two target strengths (namely, 25 MPa and 65 MPa) are assumed for RAC and aggregate replacement up to 50% is considered.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Materials

Since this study focuses on aggregates, a detailed characterization of their properties was carried out. NAs were subdivided into a fine fraction, made of quartz sand, with nominal diameter smaller than 4.75 mm, and coarse granite stones, with nominal diameter ranging between 4.75 mm and 9.5 mm. Conversely, RCAs were obtained by crushing the debris of RC beams produced and already tested in laboratory: in a first stage,

the source concrete was broken into smaller pieces by means of a stone crusher and, then, a jaw crusher was used to further reduce the particle dimensions. Moreover, the well-known longitudinal blending bed technique was adopted for homogenizing the particles. Finally, they were sundried and sieved to obtain coarse RCAs with a nominal diameter ranging between 4.75 mm and 9.5 mm. Figure 1 shows the three types of aggregate used in this study.

Figure 1. Aggregate fractions: (a) fine NAs, (b) coarse NAs and (c) RCAs.

Several tests were carried out for characterizing both natural and recycled aggregates. Particularly, both specific gravity and water absorption tests were performed on coarse NAs and RCAs according to NBR NM 53 (2009). Moreover, the same properties of NFA were determined according to NBR NM 52 (2009) and NBR NM 30 (2001), respectively. Further tests were required for determining parameters identifying the aggregates' properties, as part of the mix-design methodology adopted in this study. Table 1 reports the results of the aforementioned tests executed on both NAs and RCAs.

Table 1. Properties of the aggregates used in this study.

Properties	Fine aggregate		Coarse aggregate	
	NA	NA	RCA	RCA
Maximum grain size (mm)	4.75	9.5	9.5	9.5
Specific gravity (kg/m ³)	2405.0	2639.5	2571.2	2571.2
Water absorption (%)	0.45	1.2	8.0	8.0
Water absorption in 10 minutes (%)				5.6
Compactness	Class 1	0.671	0.570	0.501
	Class 2	0.753	0.558	0.488
	Class 3	0.741	0.678	0.506
CPM parameters	"p"	0.8092	0.9885	0.9665
	"q" (MPa)	0.00000	0.00466	0.00666

First, the "compactness" of aggregates was determined by means of a combination of mechanical compression and vibration processes (de Larrard, 2009). For the sake of accuracy, these tests were carried out separately on the following size "classes" of coarse aggregates:

- class 1: diameter bigger than 7.93 mm;
- class 2: diameter between 6.30 to 7.93 mm;
- class 3: diameter smaller than 6.30 mm;

and fine aggregate:

- class 1: diameter bigger than 2.36 mm;
- class 2: diameter between 1.18 to 2.36 mm;

- class 3: diameter smaller than 1.18 mm.

Then, the two parameters “p” and “q”, also requested by the adopted mix-design methodology (Section 2.2), were determined: in principle, “p” represents the bond between aggregate and paste, whereas “q” identifies the intrinsic strength of aggregates.

As for the binder, a high initial strength Portland cement, labeled CPV-ARI according to the National Brazilian Standard (NBR) 5733 (1991), with compressive strength of 50 MPa at 28 days and specific gravity equal to 3170 kg/m³ was used in the present study.

Furthermore, polycarboxilate superplasticizer (Glenium 51) was employed for controlling workability: its presents a solid content of 30% and specific gravity of 1087 kg/m³.

Finally, as regards the reinforcement, deformed steel rebar with a diameter of 6.3 and 20 mm were used in this study. The main mechanical properties, directly determined through tensile tests, reported hereafter: yield stress $f_{sy}=540$ MPa, ultimate strength $f_{su}=705$ MPa and elastic modulus $E_s=232.9$ GPa.

2.2 Concrete mixtures composition

The concrete mixtures compositions were designed according to the Compressible Packing Model (CPM) (de Larrard, 1999): it assumes that the overall packing density achieved by the granular skeleton controls the resulting properties of concrete. The software *BetonLab Pro 3* was employed for running the analyses requested by CPM.

Two different target compressive strengths were considered: 25 MPa and 65 MPa; moreover, for each of them, two mixtures were designed: a reference concrete with only NAs and a RAC mixture with 50% (in volume) of coarse NAs replaced by RCAs.

Table 2 summarizes the compositions of the four concrete mixtures: they are labelled as “CXX-YY”, where “XX” indicates the strength class (25 or 65) and “YY” indicates the RCA level (00 for the reference concrete, and 50 for the RACs). The superplasticizer was used in weight equal to 1% of the cement weight in all concrete mixtures. It is worth to highlight that in the RAC mixtures the NCAs were not simply replaced by RCAs, in fact, the CPM defines the optimal compactness for each mixture considering the individual properties of each compound in order to achieve the desired strength (i.e., 25 MPa and 65 MPa).

Table 2. Concrete mixture compositions.

Concretes	25 MPa		65 MPa	
	C25-00	C25-50	C65-00	C65-50
Replacement ratio (%)	0	50	0	50
Coarse NA (kg/m ³)	923	468	883	432
RCA (kg/m ³)	0	394	0	364
Fine NA (kg/m ³)	841	852	742	787
Cement (kg/m ³)	304	294	531	503
Water (kg/m ³)	206	213	185	193
W/C	0.68	0.72	0.35	0.38

It is worth highlighting that the higher water in RAC mixtures is due to the higher water absorption capacity of RACs with respect to NAs: the water absorption capacity after 10 minutes of immersion was actually considered in the mix design (Table 1).

2.3 Mixing procedure

The mixing procedure was developed throughout the following stages:

- coarse and fine aggregates were mixed for one minute;
- 50% of the total water was added and mixing continued for one more minute;
- the cement was added and the constituents were mixed for one further minute
- both the second half of water and the superplasticizer were added and the whole constituents were mixed for other 8 minutes.

Cylindrical samples (100 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height) of the concrete mixtures were taken out. The fresh concrete was always compacted by means of a vibrating table in three steps of 30s each. Moreover, the samples were demolded after 24h and, hence, cured at 21°C and 100% humidity until the age of testing.

Moreover, one beam specimens (150 mm x 350 mm x 1700 mm) were cast for each concrete mixture were tested: Figure 2 shows the relevant geometric properties, as well as the longitudinal and transversal reinforcement of the aforementioned beams.

Figure 2. Beam reinforcement.

2.4 Experimental program and testing procedures

Slump tests were performed for all mixtures according to the NBR NM 67 (1998). Compression tests were carried out on cylindrical specimens after 28 days of curing, according to the NBR 5739 (2007): four specimens were actually tested for each mixture. Tensile splitting tests were also performed at 28 days, according to the NBR 7222 (2011), on four specimens for each mixture. The specimens were tested on a 1000 kN Shimadzu testing machine at a rate of axial displacement of 0.1 mm/min for the compressive tests and 0.3 mm/min for the tensile splitting tests.

As for the three-point bending tests, they were performed on the beam supported on a span length of 85 cm: the vertical deflection was imposed at a rate of 0.3 mm/min. Figure 3 describes the measurement equipment employed in the performed tests.

Figure 3. Beam test set-up and dimensions.

The following devices were intended at monitoring the evolution of strains and crack opening:

- 2 strain-gages in the center of the reinforcing inferior steel rebars;
- 4 strain-gages on the concrete surface: two in central-top region (S1 and S2), and two in the mid span section, at mid-height (S3) and on the bottom surface (S4);
- 1 LVDT for the vertical deflection (L1);
- 2 LVDTs in the lateral surface of the beam, intended at measuring the crack opening due to shear stresses (L2 and L3).

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Properties of RAC at fresh and hardened states

Table 3 reports mean values (and coefficient of variations) of slump, 28-days compressive strength $f_{c,28}$, strain at maximum stress ϵ_c , elastic modulus E_c , and splitting tensile strength f_t determined on the cylindrical specimens of the four mixtures under consideration. Slump tests show values slightly larger than 100 mm for all the concrete mixtures, which actually allows an appropriate casting of concrete.

Table 3. Rheological and mechanical properties of concrete mixtures.

Mix	Slump (mm)	$f_{c,28}$ (MPa)	ϵ_c ($\mu\epsilon$)	E_c (GPa)	f_t (MPa)
C25-00	115	27.5($\pm 4.2\%$)	2290($\pm 2.1\%$)	20.8($\pm 7.4\%$)	2.98($\pm 7.7\%$)
C25-50	120	26.5($\pm 4.8\%$)	2310($\pm 3.9\%$)	21.8($\pm 5.5\%$)	3.02($\pm 5.6\%$)
C65-00	120	67.5($\pm 2.9\%$)	3005($\pm 2.5\%$)	30,0($\pm 4.2\%$)	5.05($\pm 3.0\%$)
C65-50	100	65.8($\pm 3.9\%$)	3115($\pm 4.6\%$)	31.4($\pm 4.8\%$)	5.16($\pm 2.6\%$)

Table 3 highlights that all mixtures achieved the target strengths $f_{c,28}$ assumed to the design stage. Moreover, since the values of ϵ_c and E_c for both reference concrete and RAC are very close in the two mixtures designed for both normal (25 MPa) and high strength (65 MPa) strength, it can be asserted that, in these mixtures, RACs does not significantly influence the stress-strain curve of materials (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Typical stress-strain curves of concrete in compression at 28 days.

As for cracking, normal strength specimens exhibited several thin diagonal cracks and the specimens maintained their initial cylindrical appearance (Figure 5a), whereas high strength ones resulted in explosive rupture when the maximum load was reached and the specimens lost their initial cylindrical appearance (see Figure 5b).

Figure 5. Typical cracks developed in specimens subjected to compression: (a) normal strength concrete (C25) and (b) high strength concrete (C65).

Overall, all the qualitative and quantitative considerations pointed out above highlight that no significant differences arose between reference concretes and RACs under investigations: this is a result of the adopted mix-design methodology, which considered explicitly the special features of RCAs and their different properties with respect to ordinary NAs.

3.2 Flexural behavior of RC beams

Table 4 reports the values of the key parameters obtained in the three-point bending tests carried out on the beams depicted in Figures 2 and 3. As expected, all the tested specimens failed in shear. As for the normal-strength beams C25-XX, the RAC beam (C25-50) reached a shear strength slightly lower (about 5%) than the corresponding reference specimen (C25-00). Conversely, a small increase in shear strength (about 4%) was observed for the high-strength RAC beam (C65-50) with respect to the reference specimen (C65-00). Similar observations could be pointed out in terms of force resulting in the first crack formation.

Table 4. Main results of the three-point beam tests.

Concrete mixtures	First crack		Failure		Crack width on the crack side (mm)
	Force (kN)	Deflection (mm)	Force (kN)	Deflection (mm)	
C25-00	154.0	0.42	496.0	1.26	3.02
C25-50	137.2	0.48	468.6	1.55	3.87
C65-00	225.0	0.87	704.4	2.72	4.85
C65-50	234.1	1.23	734.1	4.07	5.21

Figure 6 plots the force-displacement curves obtained in the aforementioned three-point bending tests: it shows the slightly higher bending stiffness exhibited by the two reference beams with respect to the corresponding RAC specimens. However, the difference in terms of both stiffness and strength exhibited in Figure 6 and reported in Table 4 can be justified by the natural variability of material properties.

Further elements, useful for understanding the mechanical response of the beams tested in bending, can be drawn out of Figures 7 and 8, which depict the crack patterns captured at the end of the tests on the four beams under consideration.

Figure 6. Force-deflection curves for normal- (C25) and high-strength concretes (C65).

Figure 7. Final crack pattern of the beams made of C25 concrete

Figure 8. Final crack pattern for the beams made of C65 concrete

As expected in short members, two concrete struts, connecting the loaded point to the two supports, are formed and shear failure is basically controlled by concrete crushing. Therefore, the shear response of the tested beams is controlled by concrete crushing and no negative influence of RAC can be observed in the tested beams, as the variations in terms of shear strength are basically in the same order of magnitude of the variations observed on the compressive strength of materials (Table 3).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study reported the results of some experimental tests carried out on concrete of different strength including RCAs in partial replacement of the coarse NAs. The following comments, partially contrasting with the conclusions of other studies available in the literature (Section 1) can be remarked:

- Both normal- and high-strength concrete can be realized by replacing significant portions of NAs, provided that an appropriate methodology is adopted for the design of the mixture taking into account the peculiar features of RCAs;
- The well-known Compressible Packing Model, originally formulated for ordinary structural concrete, confirms its accuracy and reliability in the case of the RAC mixtures considered in this study;
- Consequently, no quantitatively significant variations are observed for RACs and the corresponding reference concrete mixtures, neither in terms of workability at the fresh state, nor in strengths and stiffness at the hardened states;
- Beyond the mean values of the aforementioned mechanical parameters, the very small coefficients of variation determined for the RACs' properties suggest that the latter are sufficiently predictable and, hence, RAC can be safely employed in field applications;
- As for the structural performance, the comparable mechanical behavior of materials reverberates on the resulting shear strength of the tested RC beams: no negative structural effect is induced by the presence of RCAs.

Finally, it is worth highlighting that, on the one hand, the encouraging conclusions itemized above are due to the proper mixture design methodology adopted for RAC, and, on the other hand, further experimental tests, exploring a wider parametric field, are needed to confirm the preliminary results obtained in this study.

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REFERENCES

- Arezoumandi, M., Smith, A., Volz, J.S, and Khayat, K.H. (2015), "An experimental study on flexural strength of reinforced concrete beams with 100% recycled concrete aggregate", *Engineering Structures*, 88, 154-162.
- Arezoumandi, M., Volz, J., and Myers, J. (2013). "Shear Behavior of High-Volume Fly Ash Concrete versus Conventional Concrete", *ASCE Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 1506-1513.

- de Larrard, F. (1999) Concrete mixture proportioning: a scientific approach. E&FN Spon, London and New York, 1999.
- Fathifazl, G., Abbas, A., Razaqpur, A.G, Isgor, O.B., Fournier, B., and Foo S. (2006). “New mixture proportioning method for concrete made with coarse recycled concrete aggregate”, *ASCE Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 21(10), 601-611.
- HKBD (2009), *Use of Recycled Aggregates in Concrete*, Hong Kong Buildings Department.
- Kenai, S., & Debieb, F. (2015). Mechanical properties and durability of concrete made with coarse and fine recycled concrete aggregates. *Magazine of Concrete Research*, 67(12), 621-632.
- Koenders, E.A.B., Pepe, M., and Martinelli E. (2014). “Compressive strength and hydration processes of concrete with recycled aggregates”, *Cement and Concrete Research*, 56, 203–212.
- López Gayarre, F., López-Colina Pérez, C., Serrano López M.A., Cabo A.D. (2014). “The effect of curing conditions on the compressive strength of recycled aggregate concrete”, *Construction and Building Materials*, 53(28), 260-266.
- Meyer, R (2009), “The greening of the concrete industry”, *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 31(8), 601-605.
- MIITT (2008), *Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni*, Italian Ministry for Infrastructure and Transportation, Decree (in Italian).
- Moll, S., Bringezu, S., and Schütz, H. (2005). *Resource Use in European Countries—Material Flows and Resource Management*, Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and, Energy, Wuppertal (DE), 2005.
- NBR 5733 (1991) Cimento Portland com Alta Resistencia Inicial. Rio de Janeiro.
- NBR 5739 (2007) Concreto - Ensaio de compressão de corpos-de-prova cilíndricos. Rio de Janeiro.
- NBR 7222 (2011) Concreto e argamassa - Determinação da resistência à tração por compressão diametral de corpos-de-prova cilíndricos. Rio de Janeiro.
- NBR NM 30 (2001) Determinação da absorção de água em agregados miúdos. Rio de Janeiro.
- NBR NM 52 (2009) Agregado miúdo - Determinação da massa específica e massa específica aparente. Rio de Janeiro.
- NBR NM 53 (2009). Agregado graúdo – Determinação da massa específica, massa específica aparente e absorção de água. Rio de Janeiro.
- NBR NM 67 (1998) Concreto – Determinação da consistência pelo abatimento do tronco de cone. Rio de Janeiro.
- Pacheco, J., de Brito, J., Ferreira, J., and Soares, D. (2015). “Flexural load tests of full-scale recycled aggregates concrete structures”, *Construction and Building Materials*, 101, 65-71.
- Pepe, M., Toledo Filho, R.D., Koenders E.A.B., Martinelli E. (2014), “Alternative processing procedures for recycled aggregates in structural concrete”, *Construction and Building Materials*, 69, 124-132.
- Sadati, S., Arezoumandi, M., Khayat, K.H., and Volz J.S. (2016). “Shear Performance of Reinforced Concrete Beams Incorporating Recycled Concrete Aggregate and High-Volume Fly Ash”, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 115:284-293.